

**PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONAL AND
PEDAGOGICAL QUALITIES OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS**

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Abstract: In this article, the author describes the requirements for the level of theoretical and practical knowledge received today by graduates of higher educational institutions, that is, future specialists, the organization of their training based on an integrative approach, the implementation of thoughts in this area, information was given about ongoing reforms and tasks.

Keywords: integration, approach, future specialist, education, upbringing, form of education, continuity, activity, independent thinking, personality-oriented education.

Introduction. The independence reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan require the implementation of serious changes in the economic, political, spiritual, ideological, and cultural reforms in the educational system.

It is known that in the conditions of today's globalization, the rise, development, or, on the contrary, the crisis of each country depends in every way on the level of development of the education system in that country. An educational system capable of functioning by these qualities is needed for modern society and for the economic, social, and political relations that are becoming free.

The main part. We know that the higher education system is undoubtedly considered a priority direction in the field of social development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Therefore, the Law "On Education" states that admission to educational institutions is carried out based on the principle of providing equal opportunities for education for all applicants [1].

In recent years, the use of person-oriented technologies in the education system, helping students to show their unique talents, forming students as individuals and subjects, their mental and spiritual development, and spiritual-ethical, aesthetic, and physical education regulatory frameworks are being created. By the state requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age and taking into account advanced foreign experience, the tasks of creating conditions for children to develop intellectually, morally, aesthetically, and physically in all aspects were set as a priority. As a result, the pedagogical possibilities of expanding the field of metacognitive knowledge of students, applying empathy-based person-oriented technologies to the educational process, and improving them have expanded.

Today, new approaches are being actively introduced in the field of education in our country, new types of educational organizations, in particular, specialized educational institutions, presidential schools, and creativity schools, are being established, and have studied the world experience and along with the introduction of new procedures, modern educational methods, the socio-pedagogical necessity of applying person-oriented technologies to educational didactics is based.

Person-oriented education is a system that can demonstrate educational opportunities aimed at the development, socialization, and training of independent, critical, and creative thinking skills in modern conditions according to all the possibilities of the educational process.

In modern pedagogy, the professional importance of the teacher is determined by knowing how to organize the process of forming the psychological qualities of the student in interaction with society at the level of modern achievements of culture. In this case, the main goal of interaction is the maximum development of the individual and at this level of development, a person enters the content of social life. In turn, we reflect on the factors of the development of personal and pedagogical qualities of future specialists in Figure 1 below:

Figure -1. Factors of development of personal and pedagogical qualities of Future Specialists

The issue of future specialists in the educational system determines the priority of the axiological approach in education to the democratic foundations of social relations. The humanistic approach to man expressed attention to real personal-psychological actions that increase the value of human activity, that is, to achieve one or another result. The harmonious embodiment of necessary and free, social and subjective in human education can only rely on the principles of universality in the educational process.

A modern subject of society is considered to develop a certain way of life, it is suitable for a person to open his possibilities, to realize his essential characteristics. As the final task of personal-pedagogical educational effects of future specialists, the following results are important in the formation of the following developmental qualities of the subject:

- compatibility of future specialists with human achievements in society;
- relevance of personal life activities to human problems;
- human orientation as the highest value of modern culture;
- peculiarities of individual qualities are important.

So, pedagogical conditions relate to the concepts of development, spirituality, and morality, which significantly characterize the subject of activity.

Work experience in higher education institutions of pedagogy confirms the confirmation of teaching methods of social and humanities that develop students' dialectical thoughts, teach them to come to the necessary conclusions independently, to generalize, to understand the essence of events, to use knowledge for a principled assessment of the events of the past and present. emphasizes. Thus, it shows that in the modern higher education system, positive changes are being observed in the formation of the scientific and humanitarian outlook of future specialists.

Increasing attention to the methodological foundations of specialized disciplines in the development of personal and pedagogical qualities of future specialists. In the process of training future teachers, they will give up traditional material and introduce the interpretation of issues related to the worldview of science into the educational information. It is recognized that an important criterion of the effectiveness of teaching social and humanitarian sciences is the transition of social knowledge to an active factor of individual consciousness, to deep personal beliefs. The formation of a worldview is not a short-term, but a multi-level process, in which each academic subject should have a specific place and respond to solving specific tasks. The scientific-humanistic worldview of the history teacher is considered the most relevant in the field of his preparation for the subject, in which professional beliefs related to the aspects of the history teacher-pedagogical specialty can be effectively formed.

Therefore, the following aspects are of great importance for the formation of the outlook on the development of personal and pedagogical qualities of future specialists:

The outlook of future specialists reflects the synthesis of two levels of the individual's consciousness - ideology and psychology, external and internal, objective and subjective;

formation of the personal-pedagogical outlook of future specialists depends on the formation of civil and professional-methodical knowledge of the pedagogue;

the process of forming the personal-pedagogical, scientific-humanitarian worldview of future specialists is related to the interrelationship of the intellectual and spiritual-ethical formation of a person;

The ability to form professionally relevant beliefs is determined by the ability to:

- a) know how to analyze and understand the positive content of history;
- b) ability to generalize;
- c) understanding the essence of historical events;
- d) use of knowledge for a principled assessment of past and present events;

the field of subject training of a pedagogue is the most important for the formation of his professional beliefs.

In conclusion, the teaching profession is one of the most honorable professions. Therefore, studying the pedagogical aspects of the development of personal and pedagogical qualities of future specialists in higher educational institutions is one of the main issues.

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